

Supplementary Materials: The Origins of Texture Development in the α and β Phases during Hot-Rolling of a Zr-2.5Nb Alloy

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Figure 1: Optical polarised light micrographs of the initial Zr-2.5Nb alloy starting microstructure, showing the outline of large prior- β grains (left) and the formation of Widmanstätten α -laths (right) at room temperature.

Figure 2: Starting forged Zr-2.5Nb material. The α -phase orientations are indexed using EBSD, showing (a) orientation map of the Widmanstätten laths and (b) accompanying $\{0002\}$, $\{10\bar{1}0\}$ and $\{11\bar{2}0\}$ pole figures. The β orientations are reconstructed using a software algorithm, showing (c) orientation map of the high temperature β grains and (d) accompanying ODF slice at $\phi_2 = 45^\circ$. The EBSD map is taken with respect to the subsequent rolling directions, in the RD-ND plane (TD direction) and with inverse pole figure (IPF) colouring in TD, covering an area of 145 mm^2 at a step size of $5 \mu\text{m}$. The prior- β grains labelled 1, 2 and 3 are analysed separately in the discussion.

Figure 3: EBSD orientation map following rolling at 800°C to 75% reduction, showing indexed α orientations (a) within a β -grain with a $\{111\}\langle 110 \rangle$ γ -fibre component (b). Within the local micro-texture kinking and breakup of α -grains with $0002 \parallel \text{RD}$ and $0002 \parallel \text{ND/RD}$ orientations can be seen.

Figure 4: Fine-scale EBSD orientation map taken after rolling at 800°C to 87.5% reduction and annealing heat-treatment (HT) at 750°C for 2 hours, taken in the RD-ND plane (TD direction), showing growth of primary α , mostly with $0002 \parallel$ TD.